
Innovation in entrepreneurship at the time of covid-19: Development in economic persistence of Morocco

Auteur 1 : Oussama ATTAHIR,

Oussama ATTAHIR 1, (PhD in Economic Science)
Faculty of Juridical, Economic and Social Science of Agadir,
University of Ibn Zohr Agadir, Morocco

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Abstract:

The covid-19 crisis described as unprecedented has exceeded its health field while collapsing the entire global economic system. Morocco, meanwhile, has suffered very aggressive effects on both the economic and social aspects.

The economic decline of a large number of VSEs and SMEs is mainly due to temporary and/or permanent interruption of activities.

Faced with the challenges of economic recovery, sustainable territorial economic development and the sustainability of companies in times of crisis. Innovation is essential for Moroccan companies, as well as for project leaders, especially in terms of the development of new products, processes, innovative management styles, etc. as a major lever for development.

The development of our contribution will revolve around highlighting the attractiveness territory, to study deeply the innovative intelligence of Moroccan economic actors. We will also focus on the key position of innovation at the heart of the roadmap developed by Moroccan public and private entities to overcome the effects of the crisis, strengthening entrepreneurship and ensuring the development of an economy strong regionally, sustainable, forward-looking and high value-added.

Keywords:

Territorial attractiveness; Crisis; Innovation; Entrepreneurial anchoring; Economic sustainability

1. Introduction:

The pandemic crisis, which has seriously disrupted all sectors of the Moroccan economic system, has accelerated the need for public and private actors to intervene to get the national economy back on track develop its attractiveness and promote regional dynamism.

In order to overcome the devastating consequences of the health crisis, Morocco is moving forward towards the encouragement, strengthening and intensification of innovative initiatives. To this goal, a revitalization of regionalization, based on forms of participation and organisational cohesion between all territorial public and private actors is essential. In other words, it is a question of promoting the attractiveness of territories, through the strengthening of economic activities in all regions of the country by the encouragement of innovative entrepreneurial activities.

The success of the entrepreneurial ecosystem depends largely on the will of companies and young promoters, as well as that of the authorities, which is reflected in the ambitions of the public authorities through the new development model. It is in this line that the demand for differentialist innovations is now considered a determining factor in the creativity of very small and medium-sized Moroccan enterprises allowing them on the one hand to adapt to the context of crisis, and on the other hand, to be able to withstand increasingly fierce competition in an intensely competitive environment, globalized and changing.

In this regard, our research question is to know "To what extent do territorial attractiveness and innovation strengthen entrepreneurial activities?". In the field of sustainable entrepreneurship, the contribution of economic actors should in principle not be limited to the development of financial capital, that is to say, to the achievement of financial performance, but should also ensure the development of the social and environmental capital of the territories.

In order to answer our problem we put forward the following research hypotheses:

- Hypothesis 1: Because of its attractiveness, the territory would offer a favorable base for companies and young project leaders.
- Hypothesis 2: Innovation and the introduction of advanced technologies would strengthen the resilience of Moroccan companies to shocks caused by unexpected events.

I will try in this research to show the importance of innovation for sustainable economic development, even in times of major and brutal crises such as covid-19.

The working approach leads us to structure this article in two sections. The first will be devoted to an overview of the academic literature relating to the concepts of territory and territorial attractiveness. While the second section aims, initially, to highlight the role of clusters and localized production systems, to establish the attractiveness of territories and therefore stimulate Morocco's position in terms of innovation. In a second step, to demonstrate the importance of entrepreneurial innovation. And finally to highlight the role of new information and communication technologies (ICTs) and advanced technologies to enshrine sustainability and to establish the country's economic resilience.

Thus, economic recovery is one of Morocco's main priorities. In the sense that the current situation requires the involvement of all actors and the making of great efforts to revive and revitalize the national economy so as to ensure the promotion of employment.

2. Territory and territorial attractiveness in the economic literature review

Nowadays, the territory and its attractiveness are one of the key issues of public management. The interest in this area of public management is twofold. On the one hand, it seeks to use the practice of management sciences to appropriately interweave public policies carried out by the State, i.e. by public administrations and local authorities. On the other hand, it seeks to strengthen relations between all public bodies and private in order to guarantee a high degree of attractiveness and territorial anchoring.

With this in mind, the first section aims to focus on the understanding of the concept of territory, as well as to identify the notion of territorial attractiveness.

2.1. The territory: A multidisciplinary concept

Starting from the concept of territory, which is according to Pecqueur (2010) a geographical scale of coordination between actors and a dimension located between the individual and national productive systems. As for Jacquier (2009) the territory can be defined as a place composed of three fundamental elements: the place, the people and the institutions that define and guide the activities of the population belonging to the territory in question in spheres of sustainable development. This definition naturally refers to that proposed by Médard (1969) who, for his part, considers the territory as a community reality, in other words, as a place in which people interact and share a common life under the regulation of the institutions.

In addition, the territory presents a certain complexity, as shown by the definition developed by Moine (2006), it is a complex system composed of a web of relations between people, a system of representation and a system of actors in a geographical area. The territory is understood as a space that emerges according to the success of the actors in solving the shared environmental, societal or even productive constraints (Pecqueur and Itçaina, 2012).

Today, in a context of globalization, with fierce competition, the development and enhancement of territories is a real primary necessity to reshape our economy, in particular by attracting and stimulating national and international investors. In addition, encouraging and directing young people towards entrepreneurial activities will contribute to the economic development of the country. This encouragement is likely to cushion some of the social effects caused by the crisis through job creation and the reduction of unemployment.

It is important to point out that the achievement of a harmonious level of development, integrating social, economic and environmental dimensions, depends on the involvement of all actors (territorial officials, companies, civil society ...) in a logic of coordination and participation to bring out an endogenous development project of their territories.

This line of development underpins the importance of implementing territorial policies aimed at integrating different development perspectives while taking into account sectoral logics (Massicotte, 2003).

Indeed, the transformations induced by the covid-19 crisis call for a spatial development approach that integrates three spheres, namely, economic, social and environmental. These three dimensions depend on the promotion of cooperation logics of different kinds between all territorial actors and their ability to generate innovations (Jacquier, 2008).

The current challenges lie mainly in the field of governance, where stakeholders involved in territorial management must update their strategies and strengthen their capacities to develop responses to current issues. As a result, these actors are faced with the need to put innovation at the heart of the development of policies, organizational styles, productive processes, and distribution channels.

In the same vein, Vaillancourt (2016) advocates a collective intervention involving civil society and elected officials to co-construct and institutionalize innovation in the regions.

At this stage, it is crucial to point out that the territory is no longer considered as a mere receptacle. It is conceived nowadays as a key concept that contributes strongly to the endogenization of territorial development.

It is true that this notion is polysemic and rich in meaning. In the light of the analysis of the literature, the territory can be perceived on our side as a politico-administrative division bringing together a set of public and private actors who organize themselves in the form of networks in the objective of sustainable development through creativity, innovation and performance.

At this stage, and after the exposure of certain definitions of the concept of territory. It must be noted that the notion of territory is of paramount importance, especially in a context of accelerated implementation of advanced regionalization and territorialization of development programs in Morocco. Indeed, the contribution of the territory is becoming more and more obvious to the construction of sustainable development economically and socially. We will focus below more specifically on territorial attractiveness and its anchoring.

2.2. Territorial attractiveness: Key factor for entrepreneurial success in Morocco

Turning to territorial attractiveness, the origin of which goes back to the debate on the capture of foreign capital and the establishment of subsidiaries. According to Thiard (2005), this can be explained by the efforts of nations to try to attract foreign investment, which is considered an essential lever for growth while putting nations, regions and cities in competition.

In the same vein, the broadening of the notion of attractiveness by bringing the character "multi target" and "multidisciplinarity" (Gérardin and Poirot, 2010) is perfectly explained by the fact that the concept has extended according to Damon et al., (2010) to all dimensions of what can make the quality of a space.

This part of our contribution is mainly concerned with territorial attractiveness in the economic sense. However, it is essential to point out that the economic aspect of the attractiveness of the territories also depends on the residential and tourist attractiveness, which can be described as determining the success of the residential and tourist dimension of the latter. These two dimensions are decisive for the success of territorial economic attractiveness, which seeks to cover all potential users of space (Thiard, 2005).

In addition, territorial attractiveness is understood as an objective shared by all public and private actors. This results in mutual needs between the different stakeholders. This interaction of needs is explained, on the one hand, by the fact that companies depend on their location in territories with the means and resources to carry out their activities comfortably. In turn, the territories are expected to have the largest number of businesses that will improve the quality

of life of residents and attract more domestic and foreign investors. And, infine to the creation of wealth and jobs in the territory.

In addition, an attractive territory is a territory with the basic conditions of attractiveness, which can be qualified as material and/or ideal resources (Pecqueur and Gumuchian, 2007), namely:

- First, raw materials, infrastructure (road, sea, air, etc.) allowing a fluid interconnection with other territories and also easy access to markets.
- Secondly, professional and university training centres enabling the preparation of a competent and qualified workforce, engineers, managers, etc. capable of bringing added value to the various organisations that make up the territory;
- Thirdly, research and development (R&D) centres ensuring the increase of innovation potential, knowledge and know-how.

The combination of these resources will make it possible to guarantee "territorial biodiversity", which, according to Bessière (1998) is considered a factor of "construction and territorial affirmation".

In this regard, and in the current geoeconomic context, the resources built by the territory constitute a strategic variable for its development and competitiveness.

It is essential, at this stage, to set up territorial intelligence systems based on the valorization and emergence of built resources, including knowledge, competence and organization, which are now as links in the development of territories.

In general, territorial attractiveness can be understood as the ability of territories to attract economic and social actors. The latter are valuable since they participate in the construction of sustainable economic and social development. However, this territorial attractiveness must be complemented by anchoring, that is to say, it is not a question of attracting companies to locate and establish themselves, but rather to retain and keep them permanently on the territory. It is then a question of making sure to transform the attractiveness into territorial anchoring while tracing a trajectory of development common to companies and the territory.

At this level, and after briefly explaining territorial attractiveness, it is very important to note that, according to Benko (1999), territories compete and operate in a competitive advantage regime, especially in the context of an increasingly globalized economy. Zimmermann (2005), for his part, points to the fact that territories find themselves in a competitive logic that ignores the nation-state.

Under the influence of territorial competition and the effects of the health crisis, territorial marketing is becoming an imperative for territorial actors. This kind of marketing ensures the

promotion of the image of the territories by public administrations and elected officials through the mobilization, in an organized way, of the resources and means existing on the territory. The ultimate goal is to endow the territory with a particular identity image. Such an objective can only be achieved through the achievement of sustainable territorial development. The latter involves the combination of several factors: ecological, social, institutional, economic, etc.

This is where the importance of local production systems (LPS) and clusters to improve the triptych comes in: innovation, attractiveness and competitiveness of territories.

In the same vein, the coupling between elected officials / managers is strongly recommended to those responsible for the quality of territories in order to establish a common culture on territorial attractiveness while involving, at the same time, all public and private actors as well as citizens. In the same sense, we refer to the position of Hernandez (2006-2008), which, according to the movements of deconcentration and decentralization lead the territories to take charge of their own destinies.

In the same vein, the orientation of territories through the implementation of instruments and policies oriented towards an objective of attractiveness in a concern for territorial competitive advantage ensures the distinction between competitors (Thisse and Ypersele, 1999; Camagni, 2005, 2006; Gérardin and Poirot, 2010).

3. Local Production Systems (LPS) & Clusters: Levers for valorization, development, growth and triggers for innovation in a crisis context

In the era of crisis, the Moroccan government is making colossal efforts while seeking to redress the country's economic situation. In this context, the revival of public policies guaranteeing the valorization of territories, their skills and their resources (natural, material and built), to propel the national economy ahead, is one of the strategic choices. In other words, it is no longer possible to react to the negative effects of the health crisis, without going through a regionalized and territorialized response ensuring the creation of a sustainable economic performance.

At this level, and before addressing the importance of SPLs and clusters, two important questions can be asked:

- Do SPLs and clusters promote territorial attractiveness?
- How is the revelation and strengthening of innovation are ensured by SPLs and clusters?

To answer our questions, it is important to understand, in the first place, SPL and clusters. And to study, subsequently, the contribution of the latter to the promotion of innovative entrepreneurial activities.

3.1. SPL & Clusters: Levers for entrepreneurial development and growth

The question of the form of territorial economic organization is of growing interest to the research community. The integration of geographical data (of spaces) is increasingly taking an increasing place in the trial of understanding economic phenomena. For our part, we will try throughout this second part to demonstrate the role of SPLs and clusters in the economic development of nations, especially in Morocco.

First, the notion of Localized Productive System (PLC) which is also called Local Production System derives from that of industrial district, which, according to Marshall (1890) is a set of production systems bringing together a colossal number of SMEs and SMIs grouped geographically and contributing to the production of homogeneous products.

According to Datar (2002), SPL are productive and interdependent organizations with similar or even complementary activities. These organizations that distribute among themselves the work of production are located on the same territory corresponding to a basin of employment. In addition, SPLs can be built around different companies, whether SMEs and/or large companies. These enterprises are not necessarily concentrated in one branch, or specialized in different stages of the production process of the same product.

The existence of SPLs in a territory promotes economic efficiency, cohesion and leverage effects by multiplying public-private partnerships and ultimately makes it possible to develop strategic cooperation and alliances (Lartigue et al. 2008). However, SPLs can be defined as the integration of three criteria: network integration, learning dynamics and territorial anchoring (Carton et al. 2006).

Second, the term cluster has its origins in the book "The Competitive Advantages of Nations" by Professor M. Porter. According to him, the cluster is understood as "a geographical concentration of interrelated companies, specialized suppliers, service providers, related industry firms and associated institutions, in a particular field, that compete and cooperate", Cited by (Rajae Amine, 2016).

Further attempts to define the term have been attributed to the cluster concept. Rosenfeld (2002) defined it as a mass of companies that forge systematic relationships with each other based on

complementarity and similarity in a limited geographical area and contributing to the attraction of services, resources and specialized suppliers. The cluster is a concentration of a specific set of interconnected actors, in particular, industrial companies, research and development organizations and as well as universities, which strive to share a common vision of growth dynamics and common strategies for economic or technological development aimed at areas of excellence.

In this regard, the presence of clusters and SPLs in the territories cannot be neglected and is increasingly important, especially in the contribution of favorably reviving the Moroccan economy, which is constantly evolving in a globalized business world.

It must be noted, at this level, that improving the collaborative dynamic between the economic and institutional actors of the territory contributes to strengthening innovation capacities as well as to the long-term competitiveness of organizations. In this regard, Bocquet and Mothe (2009) state that at the territorial level, the creation of wealth and jobs is often implied as the final objective of the territories.

Let us now turn to the role of innovation and new technologies in the success of economic recovery, especially in a post-crisis context that is also characterized by a strong globalization of business.

3.2. Innovation & Artificial Intelligence (AI): Catalysts for entrepreneurial actions & indicators of progress and economic resilience

In the search for the sustainable development of territories, the introduction of an ambitious and more systematic vision in terms of innovation seems essential.

In this regard, it is important to note that according to the results of the Global Innovation Index 2021 published by the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), Morocco has lost two places in the world ranking of the most innovative States, It is now at the 77th position.

In the same vein, WIPO affirms through its Director Daren Tang that sectors that have relied on digitalization, technology and innovation have resisted well in the face of the harmful effects of the health crisis. Hence the positive effect of innovation and AI. In this case, strengthening the adoption of information and communication technologies (ICTs) at the heart of the daily management of Moroccan companies is a strong need to ensure their survival as well as the achievement of satisfactory results.

In addition, calling on the latter to excel more and more in areas related to innovation and advanced technologies, condition the success of the recovery of the Moroccan economy on track especially in the purpose of adapting both to the post-crisis context and to the new industrial generation, namely Industry 4.0 which marks the fourth industrial revolution.

This new era of industry can be understood, first of all as the digitization of the means of production and economic models. Secondly, as the mobilisation of modes of conception, dissemination, exploitation and regulation of innovation. And finally, like the use of new technologies within companies. According to Hirsch-Kreinsen (2018), Industry 4.0 is based on the development of cutting-edge technologies and is a technical utopia.

The application of this industrial generation will allow SMEs and VSEs to generate a leap in innovation. However, its implementation remains difficult especially as it requires a number of preparation scenarios such as, the development of technology roadmaps, the creation of specific competence centers for generation 4.0 as well as control factories, the launch of public research programs promoting the professionalization of Moroccan companies and the preparation of a platform dedicated to this new industrial generation. It is also important to engage the various actors, political, economic as well as social.

Certainly, this recent generation 4.0 should focus only on the stages of development of products and services but rather to be integrated as well into the exploitation of technologies in the technical and organizational context of work (Hirsch-Kreinsen, 2020). This is a global concern, generation 4.0 combines automation, the Internet of Things and AI that constitute technological innovations. This justifies that innovation is the basis around which new industrial and economic models of disruption are embedded.

In this regard, it seems essential to us to be interested in the impact of this generation 4.0 in relation to the economic logic that passes from mass production to that of mass customization. These value creation mechanisms are based on more flexible and on-demand production rather than on the effects of scale and quantity. In addition, this on-demand manufacturing will allow the reduction of storage and consequently the gain in terms of storage costs especially in a context of uncertainties on volumes, given the economic crisis caused by the health crisis as well as the increasing diversity of customer expectations.

It places at the heart of its logic the prediction of maintenance. It also puts at the center of these objectives a maximum adaptation of the manufacture by self-correcting the defects beforehand. This will therefore reduce waste.

In this turbulent economic context, it is important to note that, the implementation of a hybrid logic contributing to the creation of new activities based on the combination of resources, skills, technologies is highly recommended. It is also essential to encourage the openness of Moroccan companies to innovation in all its dimensions, namely innovation and creation of new products, service activities, new technical processes and digital methods (Guesnier, Le Maignan, 2006). It is from these initiatives to adopt new technologies and innovation that Morocco hopes to build growth levers around large and powerful innovation complexes.

It is important to stress that the combination of new technologies, for example, AI and robotics, will constantly promote the diversification of economic activities while stimulating manufacturing processes, such as the development of prototypes of new products as well as business processes and thus the improvement of the country's economic competitiveness. It is in this spirit of convergence, the establishment of a real innovation ecosystem and the joint mobilization of innovation and AI that the entrepreneurial dynamic is likely to develop.

Indeed, it appears that, according to a study carried out by the Moroccan Observatory of Management Practices (ONPM) that a significant number of managers (33.3% of responses) assimilate that Generation 4.0 is a set of technological tools (Internet of Things, AI, BigData, etc.) to modernize the production systems of goods and services.

However, this new vision requires complementary efforts between the State and the companies themselves in order to ensure the evolution of the latter. In the end, innovation is not only a matter of institutions; it is also and first and foremost the work of men and women, who invest in the different territories of the country.

4. Conclusion

By way of conclusion, the construction of a sustainable economic fabric capable of coping with sudden crises depends mainly on the territorial attractiveness that operates through values of coordination, cooperation, participation, empowerment and solidarity between the different actors of the territories, namely companies, universities, research organizations, etc. driven and supported by the State (Datar, 2004).

Indeed, and in addition to this context of crisis, the constraint of fierce international competition is imposed, hence the evolutionary importance of the preparation of innovative territories with favorable climates capable of attracting innovative entrepreneurial activities thus promoting the economic and social development of the country. Our theoretical contribution allowed us to test two qualitative hypotheses, which after the study of the literature asserted themselves.

- First of all, and concerning the first, the attractiveness of the territories continuously ensures the attraction both of existing companies to locate subsidiaries and to motivate young project leaders to choose the territories with the various resources, namely, natural and or built of a material, immaterial and ideological nature, as being a place conducive to the implementation of their business projects.
- Then, with regard to the second, innovation strengthens the creativity capacity of companies as well as the satisfaction of their customers through the implementation of AI tools, including cobots (collaborative robots). As a result, the resilience of Moroccan companies to shocks caused by unexpected events can be assured.

Moreover, this work constitutes a preliminary stage of research on this subject. It will be interesting to complete the study of this theme later with a field research axis aimed at comparing and analyzing the efforts of two territories (two Moroccan regions) using some criteria adopted by WIPO during the study of the innovation capacities of world economies, namely, institutions, human capital, infrastructure, creative production and dissemination of knowledge.

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